

Explore the Role of Educational Heads Regarding Secondary Schools: Perspective of Problems, Difficulties and Issues

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Abstract

Education is a positive endeavor and a financial expenditure; generally considered to be a kind of training for life. The key objectives were (a) to examine the administrative problems of secondary school heads (b) to compare the problems of the secondary schools in the rural and the urban areas. The study population was all of the Gujrat District Secondary Schools. The research sample was 64 secondary schools, 32 of which were rural and 32 were urban. Out of 32 schools in the rural 16 boys and 16 girls were further educated. Similarly, boys were sixteen and girls were sixteen out of 32 urban schools. For the educational heads of secondary schools, a questionnaire was created for data collection. For the purpose of the analysis, the percentages are used. The key purpose of the study was to identify the administrative problems, faced by high school heads that were not in fact adequately responding to the needs of the students.

Key Words:

Educational
Heads,
Administration,
Problems

Introduction

Education is an investment in human resources and has properly been built for the improvement life. Education is a profitable practice. A democratic welfare state will never neglect the fundamental socialization requirement. For this purpose, education is regarded as the main organ. Moreover, the essence of modern life has been changed and prepares the members of the state for an ever changing life.

Progressive and pragmatic worked. Although modern world has almost limitless faith in the power of education for change, however there would be no difference that no

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education system could rise above its teachers' expectations who learn and inscribe in their culture and who believe that change cannot come through rote memory.

The word "leadership" is primarily linked to the military but also to the economy and politics. Most of us learn about military administration, economic leadership, national leadership, or leadership. Leadership is the same for education as for economic leadership: "to push his people to a place they never worked." Leadership in education is a long-term endeavor dependent on knowledge, experience, persistence and a long-term perspective that can only be gained on the longer term.

Leithwood, Day, Sammons, Harris, & Hopkins (2006,2003,1999) express the importance. that school leadership, after the quality of classroom teaching, is of secondary importance to the learning. Criticism of England's schools (Whelan, 2009) Out of every 100 well run schools, 93 are going to be fine. Of the 100 schools that didn't work well, only one has strong students' results. Whelan (2009) has therefore concluded that the achievements of the students in school seldom outweigh their leadership and management

A school is a government organization responsible for the growth of its citizens, growth and support for the future citizens. It is a basic concept that without good and efficient leadership, no organization will operate smoothly and properly. The success and failure of the institutions depend upon the kind of leader it has. Professors, educational administrators, inspection officers are dependents on the collective efforts of a variety of individuals to operate effectively. A teacher must be on a good footing with the educational heads. There must be complete comprehension. A school educational heads is in charge. He has many things to perform. Sometimes he must unexpectedly determine matters, and to his assistants he might not have time to justify his decision (NCSL2007).

No school functions successfully if the teachers just work as individuals and not as a team or group. But, like any team needs a chief. A school also needs a leader who inspires and directs its employees. The educational heads must not just a dictator. "Leadership often requires accountability and the role of the educational heads is no exception to the law. Yet his leadership is much tougher as he also has people behind him who are equal to him. Within an army, officers are always superior to the average soldier. Leadership is simple in these situations, but the situation is completely different in school. Pakistan inherited a system of education, which was designed by the colonial rulers to achieve their own benefits and enslave the Hindu-Muslims of the sub-continent Indo-Pak. (NCSL2007).

Administrator during those days, assumed the role of a dictator. His subordinates as a tyrant Educational heads as educational administrator, thought also on the same line thought him of. It explains: -

What make the school system on organization are not only what is taught and how it is taught but also the inter-action of the educational heads, teachers, students and other. People in it are relationship to one another in their cooperative efforts towards a good goal (Hamid and Khalid, 1965).

"The educational heads do not follow the appropriate role for efficient management and often have problems from outside intervention. Around the same time the educational heads must be properly addressed in the same way as the educational heads' authority and duty away in the world (Govt. of Pak, 1959).

“In many communities, citizens assist and help the school and the staff with studies and problems as long as they could. Most of the citizens who have participated intelligently in such activities have not only been helpful, but have developed a good understanding of problems and responsibilities of the schools and consequently are in a position to give intelligent support to the educational program (Morphet, 1960).

In modern times the responsibilities of the school are very much enlarged and no school can justify its existence if it fails to develop the social side of the pupils. Nevertheless, teachers sometimes fail to realize the social and physical activities have to be as carefully organized and looked after as intellectual activities. They think that their main business is teaching within the classroom only, but the other aspect of pupil's training ought not to be neglected (Mohiyuddin, 1956).

The educational heads take up particularly a key and significant role in the educational as well as school system, which aims to make the educator more interested in educational management. It is the core of the connection (Spears, 1950).

There are many difficulties and problems that the educational heads of high school faces to achieve the desired education goals. Schools are more big business than ever before, making the task of the communities more unbelievably complex than ever before. The leaders face a new development in education that is discouraging. The curriculums and student activities were also older and the problems with scheduling and funding for assessment were perplexed by those activities (Spain, 1956)

As regards the educational heads/head mistress, the following quotations would serve the best to understand the significant and important role they play in the school. Everyone reports the educational heads, the man at the helm, to keep the wheel steady and the ship on a straight course. Sociologically, the role of the educational heads is to maintain the stability of the instruction. (Crovin, 1963)

The elementary school educational heads are rapidly becoming a key person in developing maintaining and improving the educational and social goals of our society. It appears from the above quotations that the head masters are the most vital factor in the instruction. It is the first and foremost duty of educational heads to create a good atmosphere in the instruction in order to promote welfare and happiness of the children. The educational heads are the leader in the school and responsible for well-being and betterment of the school.

The role of the leader in education is particularly important. The society has created schools as basic instruments for producing the kind of citizens it desires. It is undeniably true that the school administrators personally are charged with the responsibility of seeking that the school or school system operates in the best possible way (Shane, 1956).

It is quite clear that so many responsibilities rest on the heads' shoulders; therefore, they have to face too many difficulties in performing his duties. So, it is essential to be aware of these problems, because without being aware of these problems we could not expect that the school programs would be better.

The term administration has been defined differently by different writers and it has become more complicated due to recent development in social sciences. Here are some views about administration, which have been expressed by different administrations: the ability to organize so well many social forces, sometimes overlapping, in a single social entity that they act as unity. This object is the power to reorganize a set of relationships between various special interests with all of which, due to intellectual consistency, no

very highly specialized classroom is solid, and yet administration or generalization is perhaps the highest faculty of the human mind (Campbell and Gregg, 1957).

Educational administration can be described as a process of incorporating personal initiative into the use of suitable materials to effectively promote the production of human qualities. Not only are the development of children and young people involved, but also the development of adults and the growth of school people in particular (Harris, 1960).

Educational heads are the key person in school administration. They are responsible to bring the national change with his competency and unique personality. He/she is representative of department and the leader of teacher, students and community. He/she is a coordinator, helper, leader and social worker at the same moment. He/she works for teachers and students and vice versa. A dynamic society demands definite knowledge and leadership competencies for maximum educational achievements. There are certainly idealistic goal sets forth by the educationists but the realistic administrator faces certain problems in achieving them. The educational heads dealing with parents, teachers and students must know how to demonstrate his leadership skills in giving directions and imaginations to school (Shamim, 1964).

The school administrator plays a vital role in education system. They are responsible for creating a healthy atmosphere in schools to promote happiness and welfare of the children. In order to play an effective role, the educational heads must possess definite competencies and skills. The term role and competent behaviour should not necessarily be thought of as two different things (Graff and Calvin. 1957). A good manager who doesn't want anything but works for a purpose. Reciprocity and no competition can differentiate the relationships of the educational heads and the teacher. Both must agree whether or not the company fails because without another cooperation it cannot be possible (Reavis, 1942).

Research Method

The study aimed at collecting an investigation into the problems faced by high school educational heads in Gujrat district with the goal of exploring the factors that lead to various challenges.

The objective of the study was to define the disparity between the problems of high school heads employed in rural and urban regions and to assess how severe the different problems faced by secondary school heads are.

A list of the Heads of Secondary Schools was collected from the Directorate of Education Gujrat after the questionnaire was completed under guidance from the Research Advisor. Personally, the questionnaires were given to the high school heads. Researchers were faced with several hundred percent trouble returning. The proportion of participants in the study was strong. The respondents came from both urban and rural areas, which appear in the following table: -

Table 1. Respondents

Heads	Urban	Rural	Total
	32	32	64

Population

The population included all the educational heads of the high schools in the district of Gujrat.

Sample

This research included 64 high school teachers, 32 rural schools and 32 urban schools. Out of 32 rural 16 schools, boys and 16 girls Schools were also included. While, 16 schools were of boys and 16 were of girls schools from 32 urban schools.

Research Instruments

For the educational heads of secondary schools, a questionnaire was created for data collection. Personally, the questionnaires were given to the high school heads. The respondents' percentages for the study were good. The concerns were divided into teachers, students and the school's conducive environment, school services, financial, parents' departments and personal issues and AV issues. Additional issues for supports and library services.

Data Collection

Five heads of secondary schools validated the questionnaire. Their proposals have been included in the survey. The researcher himself and somewhere by mail circulated the questionnaire. This collected data from the whole schools of the sample.

Data Analysis

Data obtained by questionnaire is tabulated and the percentages are analyzed. After making interpretations, recommendations were made on the basis these findings.

Results and Discussion

The main focus of the research was to research the issues and problems of secondary school heads in Gujrat.

Questionnaire Analysis of Education Heads

Table 1. Overall Teachers Related Problems

S. No	Statements	Yes Percent	No Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	Staff Cooperation	66.7	33.3	100%
2	Obedience of Teacher	58.3	41.7	100%
3	Time Table adjustment	45.8	54.2	100%
4	Teachers transferred with permission.	58.3	41.7	100%

5	Teachers work regularly.	41.7	58.3	100%
6	Teachers participate in shared curricula	32.5	62.5	100%
7	Teachers lead class abroad	25.0	75.0	100%
8	Teachers force students to do personal business with them.	62.5	37.5	100%
9	Many teachers have experience of the subjects	29.2	70.8	100%
10	Refreshing courses to upgrade skills	41.2	58.3	100%
11	Subject wise properly qualified teachers available	37.5	62.5	100%
12	Teachers fear 9th and 10th level teaching because of ACRs.	70.8	29.2	100%
13	Teachers cover the course	70.8	29.2	100%
14	Teachers help with their teammates	58.3	41.7	100%
15	Teachers investigate students against the other teachers	54.2	45.8	100%
16	The curricula being taught	37.5	62.5	100%
17	The curricula is update	33.3	66.7	100%
18	Subjects and content being taught	62.5	37.5	100%

Above all, the teachers' problems show here that at first results improve the performance of the teachers' staff. Secondly, it demonstrates that most of the teachers are happy to always follow the order of directors. Third item revealed that managers decided that many teachers would be able to change their schedules and others did not enjoy changing the time. This ensures that their workers cannot tolerate an inappropriate schedule that triggers their teachers' achievements. The directors decided to switch teachers with the primary permission. The teachers always follow their orders.

The fifth item suggests that most of the teachers do not engage actively in co-curricular activities. The sixth point indicates that many teachers had no responsibility in the absence of the educational leaders. Some of the managers say that their instructors are not cooperative. The seventh table above reveals that a small number of school teachers are involved in actions outside the classroom. Teachers compel the students in their personal business to represent them. Most teachers don't care about the subjects. During the annual teacher years, no refresher courses were offered because the schools were missing subject specialists.

The findings show that the number of teachers is reduced in classes 9 and 10 because their grades and marks are recognized in their ACR. Teachers cover the entire course length. Leaders suggest that when they have difficulties, teachers communicate with their colleagues. It is normal for some teachers to question the other teachers. This is not periodically updated to reflect that social needs on opinion curriculum at the correct time.

The previous table and diagram indicate that 62.5% of the heads agree that updated

curricula are important to society's present and future's needs, while the remaining 37.5% disagree. It also means that several values accept that topics and material are important for the future.

Conclusions

Throughout the report, the educational heads of high schools in the Gujrat district were confronted with a survey to analyze the factors which lead to various difficulties.

1. The concerns were categorized into the staff, the students and the academic, services, finance, departmental parents, and public-person concerns and A.V.-related problems. Additional issues for supports and library services.
2. The results of the study showed that high school heads profit from their staff's cooperation and proclaimed their teachers to be proud to obey their orders. The heads said their teachers are interested in curricula and teachers cover the course.
3. 3. Most heads expressed that the shift in their time chart was not acceptable to their teachers and that their professors were not working on a daily basis without heads. All managers have assured us that teachers neither teach the classroom side by side nor force students to represent them themselves.
4. Based on the research, it was concluded that most of the heads in the school building did not address the needs of the students sufficiently and the higher authorities did not collaborate with the educational heads to solve the school problems. The study results revealed a shortage of teaching staff or menial staff in the majority of heads.
5. Most of them claimed that the students in this school did not have sufficient guiding and counselling services and the availability of general adequacy of medical facilities for the students. There was also inadequate distribution of funds for schools and students.
6. The heads were found to be deficient with audio-visual services and teaching aids. During the teachers' shift, the heads were not consulted. In those schools there were no librarians, and the research labs were not well equipped.

Recommendations

The recommendations to resolve the problems of secondary school representatives in the district of Gujrat and to improve the situation in secondary schools are as follows: The heads of secondary schools will immediately be concerned with addressing serious problems. Since the funds are not sufficient for supplying the students, it is therefore advisable to collect funds from the public.

A committee composed of representatives of the students, the teachers and the parents can be formed. As it was reported that the school staff had a heavy load of students, it was suggested that students should at least be named at every school. During the resolution of the issues, financial issues should be the focus. Both facilities, including schools, should be fitted with audio-visual devices and equipment. In order to bring parents' teachers and students closer together, teachers and other techniques of cooperation should be adopted in order to solve the problems. Additional services should be provided for rural schools. The high school leaders would take a collective approach

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and collaborate with their teachers to address the problems cooperatively. Educational heads of the administrative matters will be supported immediately by the authorities concerned.

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